

TREASURE

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Training of Early Stage Researchers: a Pilot Study

Trainings assessment and gap analysis

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Description version 1.0	This document includes the assessment and gap analysis of training resources available at the University of Coimbra (UC) to support the implementation of the previously outlined reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs within the TREASURE project milestone M.2 document (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15786164). The resources identified concern education and training programs available at the UC.

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List of Abbreviations

C.U.s *Curricular or course units*

IIIUC *Institute for Interdisciplinary Research of the University of Coimbra*

OC-P *Opportunities for collaboration: Projects*

OC-T *Opportunities for collaboration: Teaching staff*

RROR *Reproducible, reusable and open research*

UC *University of Coimbra*

TER *Training events and resources*

TREASURE *Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research Training of Early Stage Researchers*

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1. Introduction

1.1. Context and Aims

This document concerns the development and implementation of the TREASURE institutional pilot program (<https://www.uc.pt/en/iii/treasure/>) at the University of Coimbra (UC). The program aims to *enable* the implementation and adoption of more **reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR)** principles, practices and outputs across disciplines and it is applicable to all areas of knowledge, starting at earlier stages of research - master and doctoral research studies.

The TREASURE **program** consists of two optional course units (for details, see Deliverable D.2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15785597>) offered to master's and PhD candidates: the first unit, for uptake at program start, sets the enrollment in the program and the definition of the implementation plan, providing support & training; the second, to be delivered in the end of the program, will formally assess implementation of the planned practices.

For the success of this program, it is important to **identify** training resources that can support the enrolling participants in the implementation of research practices and outputs with quality. Also, it is important to take advantage of the **institutional** local context and its own **resources**, finding **gaps** when they exist.

For this, and as part of the *TREASURE project Task 4*, an **assessment** and a **gap analysis** were performed in collaboration with institutional stakeholders (local advisory board; vice-rectory for culture, communication and open science; other RROR relevant UC members).

The current document corresponds to TREASURE Milestone M.3 with the following goals:

- 1) the identification of **available resources** at the University of Coimbra considering the RROR list initially defined (Milestone M.2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15786164>). The assessment exercise targeted:
 - a. training **courses** and **resources** that could be recommended within the TREASURE program to further **support** the implementation of practices and outputs,
 - b. training **events**, either past (to identify potential **collaborators**) or future (to support implementation),
 - c. UC ongoing **projects** about or including principles and practices of open science that could provide **indirect resources** (point to future training events or resources; identify collaborators),

- d. associated **teaching staff** with whom we could **collaborate** to develop the TREASURE training program.
- 2) the performance of a **gap analysis** on practices and outputs for which no current institutional resources (training, materials, personnel) were identified - the institution could benefit from developing further expertise and resources, building skills and capacity.
- 3) inform the creation of the training & resources list (**Deliverable D.3**).

The current document details the operationalization of these goals, clarifying the **strategy** and **methodology** used to identify the resources, and detailing **resulting actions** – mapping of external resources when gaps were identified (to be included in **Deliverable D.3**) and review of the previously identified RROR list (defined in Milestone M.2 and reviewed in **Deliverable D.2**) when no resources and no training capacity was achieved. In the end, a self-reflection exercise highlights **limitations** of the approach and **lessons learned - challenges** faced during this task and **opportunities** to improve resources mapping and collaboration with existing assets for capacity building.

The TREASURE program and the exercise here performed **align** with the University of Coimbra strategic actions planned for the period 2023-2027, promoting best practices on open science and sharing of knowledge with the scientific community and society (<https://www.uc.pt/en/planning/2023/strategic-guidelines/>) and has found synergies with them in the identification of training resources (see **section 2.1.2**).

2. Identification of Training programs and resources at the University of Coimbra

2.1. Search strategy

For the identification of resources, three **approaches** (search strategies) were taken:

- 1) Definition of a **survey** to identify (a) training programs and resources, and (b) specialized personnel at the University of Coimbra;
- 2) Establishment of **synergy** with the strategic plan monitoring task by the Vice-rectory for Culture, Communication and Open Science to identify course units, training events, and projects involving principles, concepts and practices of open science;
- 3) **Additional search** to identify resources for TREASURE RROR list, complementing previous approaches by using other sources of information.

Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research training of Early Stage Researchers

FILL SURVEY

Identification of training resources and specialised personnel in the UC

Figure 1. Printsreen of the TREASURE website showing a pictorial link to the Training resources identification Questionnaire embedded in its landing page during June-July 2025 (EN version).

2.1.1. Survey

A training resources survey² was created to identify (i) **formalized** (e.g., courses, course units, certified training events) **or non-formalized training** (e.g., seminars, non-certified training events, summer/winter schools, modules, etc) and (ii) specialized **personnel** in one or more of the identified RROR practices and outputs.

Members of the **Local Advisory Board** (LAB), which represent 9 of the 11 Organic units (8 faculties), 18 courses, and 12 research & development units, were invited to participate in this task and to fill out the survey (advertised in LAB meeting and sent by e-mail). The form was also made available in the TREASURE **website** (Figure 1). Moreover, the survey was sent to the

² Available at https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf3_EjJP_15e-pzsFg36ezoShqmcsrTjDasgVWQY3sSAwfV_A/viewform

Scientific Council of the Institute for Interdisciplinary Research (IIIUC) – TREASURE’s host unit, which includes members from different R&D units across the University. Finally, the form was disseminated through an **informal group** at the UC connected to Open Science and Research Data Management topics and that include diverse members connected to ongoing initiatives and projects on these topics (ForumGDI@UC).

PRACTICES	OUTPUTS
<i>(may include or result in Outputs)</i>	<i>(should: have an persistent identifier, be accessible in a trusted repository)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author contribution statements • Unique Identifiers for research materials/resources • Stakeholder engagement, Citizen science or Participatory research • Science communication, dissemination, policy recommendations [activities, materials, policy briefs] • Using evidence synthesis techniques to assess the quality of evidence and identify research gaps • Reporting of null results • Reporting guidelines • Preregistered reproducibility or replication studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preregistration or Study design plans • Registered reports • Open step-by-step methods and protocols • Data sharing • Open source code and software • Open hardware • Open benchmarking of problems • Open/reusable materials/resources • Preprints • Open Educational materials

Figure 2. List of the reproducible, reusable, and open research practices and outputs identified during the TREASURE Research assessment framework task, together with the Local and External Advisory Boards (adapted from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15786551>).

2.1.2. Synergy with the institutional strategic & rectoral action plans

A synergy was built with the UC Strategic & Rectoral Action Plans monitoring task, by including institutionally already monitored **practices and outputs** overlapping with the TREASURE initial RROR list (**Figure 2**), namely: open materials, open source code and software (including reproducible workflows), data sharing (including research data management), stakeholder engagement (including citizen science), and open educational resources.

We took advantage of the key performance indicators - number of **course units, training events** and **projects** involving open science principles and/or practices - defined to monitor the institutional strategic guideline.

Within this approach, the following *eligibility criteria* were used: regarding curricular or **course units** (formalized training), we included only: those identified for the year 2024 and renewed for the scholar year 2025/2026, keeping in their syllabus topics explicitly covering open science principles, practices, and/or outputs; for **training events** (formalized training), we included only those carried out in 2024, with the aim of identifying collaborators (since the training had already occurred); for **projects**, we included the years monitored, 2023 and 2024, and searched for training resources coming from these projects.

2.1.3. Additional search for training using other sources of information

A manual non-exhaustive mapping was performed using other sources of information: **UC website** and **informal contacts**.

The names of practices and outputs in the original TREASURE RROR list (**Figure 2**) were used as keywords, either in Portuguese or in English, to search within the UC website (<https://www.uc.pt/>) relevant RROR related practices, events and/or projects. However, course units (and their syllabus) were not possible to cover in this search (both course units and syllabus are not accessed through UC main website search; whereas the courses dedicated platform, <https://apps.uc.pt/courses/pt/index>, does not allow to reach this sublevel of content – only courses level information).

To complement this approach, we used information identified through other means, including knowledge related with expertise of TREASURE core team members (A.S.C., C.D., J.N., I.A., T.W.) or through other sources of information (e.g., ongoing UC R&D projects; UC RROR relevant personnel).

Regarding this approach, only results for 2024 and 2025 were considered *eligible*.

2.2. Inclusion criteria

Following the eligibility criteria presented above, to be included in the training & resources list (Deliverable D.3), additional **inclusion criteria** would need to verify:

- 1) the resources refer to training that **supports** the implementation of reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) **practices or outputs**, namely those included in the TREASURE M.2 Milestone,
- 2) the source, platform for training delivery or trainer, is **trustworthy**, and/or holds **credentials** adequate to deliver the training (this criterion is hard to verify, but was based mainly on recommendations from research communities and/or experts),

- 3) the resource is **openly and freely available**, at least for master's and PhD candidates, or available through a registry or access protocol that holds no costs.

2.3. Results

A manual non-exhaustive mapping was performed for the practices and outputs identified within the TREASURE program. The results of the mapping exercise are summarized in **Table 1**, concatenating results from the three approaches taken, which sometimes overlapped.

The 3-approach strategy allowed the identification of relevant resources and personnel with RROR skills, namely **training events and resources (TER)**, i.e. training with or without assessment procedures and criteria (approaches 1, 2 and 3), e.g. course units, advanced courses with or without assessment, summer schools, advanced courses or certified training without assessment procedures, special modules within graduate programs; **opportunities for collaboration – teaching staff (OC-T)** (approaches 1, 2 and 3) and **opportunities for collaboration – projects (OC-P)** (approaches 2 and 3). OC-T were identified directly or indirectly through inspection of TER or OC-P, with the aim of establishing collaboration during TREASURE program development. They will not be included in Deliverable D.3.

2.3.1. Survey

Using the survey, seven responses were obtained, with resources identified for Author contribution statements, Using evidence synthesis techniques, Stakeholder engagement and Citizen science, Open materials, Unique and Persistent Identifiers for research materials, Data sharing, Preprints and Science communication. Resources were either course units, training events – past and future, modules or seminars, and advanced courses (TER), and UC members with RROR expertise (OC-T). Projects (OC-P) were not covered in the Survey.

Responses regarding modules that mentioned RROR practices or outputs but that were not specifically mentioned in the syllabus were considered non-formalized training (e.g. specific modules within course unit and advanced courses that are defined already during the scholar year).

2.3.2. Institutional synergy

Regarding the synergy built with the performed institutional monitoring task, identified resources covered course units, training events – past, modules or seminars, and advanced courses (TER), UC members with RROR expertise (OC-T), and projects (OC-P) – past and

ongoing. Some OC-T (personnel holding RROR expertise) were indirectly identified through TER delivery, or by being member of a project (OC-P) that involved RROR topics.

2.3.3. Additional search for training using other sources of information

This double-path search approach allowed to identify additional RROR relevant training events (TER) – future, and projects – past and ongoing (OC-P) and UC members personnel holding RROR expertise (OC-T; again, through projects, events and news). Materials such as articles and presentations (video, slides) holding a hands-on approach were also identified.

Table 1. Resources identified for each RROR practice and output, categorized into types, concatenating information coming from the three different approaches.

RROR PRACTICE OR OUTPUT	NUMBER OF RESOURCES IDENTIFIED & TYPE
Author contribution statements	TER: 4 OC-T: 2 OC-P: 1
Using evidence synthesis techniques	TER: 1 OC-T: 5
Preregistration or Study design plans	TER: 2 OC-T: 1
Registered Reports	TER: 2 OC-T: 1
Preregistered reproducibility or replication studies	OC-T: 1
Open step-by-step methods and protocols	TER: 3 OC-P: 1 OC-T: 1
Stakeholder engagement, Citizen science	TER: 3 OC-P: 7 OC-T: 7
Open materials	TER: 3 OC-P: 1 OC-T: 1
Unique and Persistent Identifiers for research materials	TER: 4 OC-T: 4
Open source code and software	TER: 2 OC-T: 9
Open benchmark problems	0
Data sharing	TER: 14 OC-P: 5 OC-T: 7
Reporting of null results	OC-T: 2

Reporting guidelines	TER: 1 OC-T: 3
Preprints	TER: 1 OC-T: 3
Science communication, public engagement, policy briefs	TER: 8 OC-T: 10
Open source hardware	0
Open educational resources	OC-T: 1

Legend: **TER**, Training events and resources; **OC-P**, Opportunities for collaboration: Projects; **OC-T**, Opportunities for collaboration: Teaching staff; **RDM**, Research Data Management; **RROR**, Reproducible, reusable and open research; **UC**, University of Coimbra.

3. Training programs and resources: Gap analysis

The **gap analysis** aimed to highlight the RROR practices and outputs identified for which no current resources (materials, personnel) were identified. **Table 1** presents a summary of the number and type of institutional resources by RROR practice and output considered in Milestone M.2 of the TREASURE program (**Figure 2**).

3.1. List of practices and/or outputs for which a gap was found

Following the mapping exercise, we identified gaps – i.e., no UC training resources nor specialized personnel were found at UC – for two of the initially defined RROR outputs in M.2:

- Open Hardware
- Open benchmark problems

As a consequence, these practices were removed from Deliverable D.2 (RROR list, assessment criteria and procedures) and will not be considered for Deliverable D.3 (Training resources list) nor for the first edition of the TREASURE program, starting in September 2025.

The removal followed the consideration that practices supported in the program should have UC personnel with RROR expertise that could guide the participant – and not relying on external resources alone.

4. Limitations & Lessons learned

4.1. Limitations

We highlight that despite the efforts and synergies achieved, this exercise resulted in a non-exhaustive mapping of institutionally available resources. In this section we summarize identified limitations in the approaches taken to identify available training resources at UC:

- Approach 1: the fact that the local advisory board does not have a full representation of all areas and departments at UC may have resulted in the survey not being widely spread. We estimate it did not reach relevant stakeholders who could have pointed out existing resources (e.g., open hardware training and expertise may exist in departments dealing with engineering sciences that are not covered in the local board)
- Approach 2: there was not a full overlap of the practices considered or the way these were defined in the institutional monitoring and the TREASURE RROR list (e.g., sometimes including diverse topics in the monitoring task, and covering one specific topic in TREASURE), which difficulted the selection of resources
- Approach 3: the additional search in UC website pages could not reach course units and their syllabus, which may have returned more formalized training and discipline-specific resources.

4.2. Lessons learned

The following challenges and opportunities were identified, contributing to learned lessons.

Challenges

- Inexistence of a UC centralized training resources repository (covering all organic and R&D units) that could be searched by keywords to facilitate findability of training connected with specific RROR topics
- Impossibility of searching by keywords in UC pages – main website and specific courses platform – to access information about course units and their syllabus
- Nomenclature of the course unit (within courses) is not always clear about its syllabus (i.e., course topics and content) when this covers explicitly RROR practices and outputs, requiring syllabus assessment of all course units from all available 1st, 2nd and 3rd courses at UC (there are 417 courses at UC)
- Syllabus is not always clear about specific RROR topics and contents as these may exist under “general” or “disciplinary” good research practices, or as normalized practices

in disciplines in which one or more RROR practices and/or outputs are already standard. Thus, one may presume the existence of course units *implicitly* covering RROR practices and principles but that are not subject to self-reflection or deliberately used as “open research”/”RROR”, training, turning the identification of RROR training resources a complex task – to deal with this, boundaries (explicit criteria) were necessarily defined so that the identification task could be feasible.

Opportunities

- Alignment of institutional monitoring tasks with TREASURE defined list of RROR practices and outputs, so that overlapping of tasks is possible without wasting time and human resources,
- Building collaboration with researchers, professors, science managers, data stewards, librarians, technical staff, etc, from different fields, involved in ongoing training projects and activities, and with expertise in different RROR principles, practices and outputs,
- Identification of challenges and barriers related with monitoring of UC RROR training capacity, allowing the development of solutions (as well of boundaries) for future exercises, assuming with iterative improvement.

5. Conclusions

The training assessment and gap analysis highlighted current training capacity and resources available at UC, but also areas in which the institution would benefit from acquiring and developing further expertise and resources, namely through train-the-trainer events or through use of external resources.

Next steps include building a training & resources list (Deliverable D.3) and setting collaborative networks - institutional, national and international – to define a more robust and iteratively improving program for successful training & implementation of more reproducible, reusable and open research practices.

For disciplines in which one or more RROR practices and /or outputs are already standard, the challenge is that they may include other RROR practices and/or outputs (when applicable) that are not yet normalized.

The ultimate goal is that RROR is embedded within and across disciplines (respecting diversity and applicability), becoming the “normal” practice.

